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Strategies of La Paz Elementary School in Community Involvement

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Abstract

The study delved on the strategies of La Paz Elementary School in community involvement in Umingan District I, Schools Division of Pangasinan II. Specifically, it determined and discussed the strategies of the school in community involvement, the strategies that contribute to the success of community involvement as perceived by the respondents; and the proposed program for the School Year 2021- 2022. As such, the findings showed that among the strategies in community involvement, parenting, communications, volunteering, learning at home, and decision-making were frequently employed by the school. Meanwhile, collaborating with the community was rarely employed by the school as strategy in community involvement. Results also revealed that the problems encountered by the school along learning at home were serious. The problems encountered by the school along parenting and volunteering were moderately serious while the problems encountered by the school along communicating, decision-making, and collaborating with the community were not serious. Further, strategies employed by the school in community involvement have significant relationships with their problems encountered along those strategies. Thus, the following activities are proposed to strengthen the strategies in community involvement in school. First, encourage parents to participate in school programs and activities especially the 4P's beneficiaries; second) give certificate of participation to parents who attend the school activities and programs; third) orient parents on the importance of parental involvement in the education of their children; fifth) orient parents on the importance of time management; and sixth) encourage parents to appreciate their children schooling by giving simple rewards whether material or non-material things.

Keywords: *community involvement strategies, collaborating with the community, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making*

Introduction

School heads and teachers are expected to be very flexible in their approach to their job as educators. Every school head should revisit their strategies which are carefully planned and carried out to better serve their stakeholders and primary customers, the learners. These strategies also vary from time to time to cope with the various needs of the community where the latter are living and to strengthen the basic framework of a quality education system which focused primarily on the success of meeting the school goals and desired outcomes towards providing the basic knowledge and 21st century skills among learners in the community (Sanders, M. 2015).

Hence, the school heads and teachers as key players in the lives of the learners and community people need also to embark a strong partnership for them to further meet the aforementioned objectives. Indeed, establishing a strong partnership and engagement with the community fosters greater relationships which result in sharing and maximizing resources. Also, this bond will help learners develop healthy behaviors and promote healthy families (Hammond et al, 2020).

Likewise, the African proverb, 'It takes a whole village to raise a child', greatly manifests to the relevance of the roles of the school and community in realizing the full potential of a child that is parallel to the Department of Education vision. Therefore, a shared mind and practice is a shared responsibility; a shared responsibility means a shared success.

Active involvement in the education of the child among the parents and community is stressed in RA 9155 otherwise known as "Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001". Participation and coordination of parents and the community within and among the schools, the local school boards, the Parents Teacher Association should be encouraged and maximized. As provided, the increased participation and involvement rate of the community in the schools will serve as a breakthrough in responding more effectively to the DepEd's goals and objectives which is quality education for all (EFA, 2015).

Consequently, the La Paz Elementary School encountered problems in parenting, communications, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making and collaborating with community. Based on the SBM Evaluation conducted in the district on November, 2019, the school obtained a numerical rating of 1.39 which describes that the level of the school is Developing. Herewith, the result signifies that the above mentioned problems are overlooked and perhaps ignored due to the lack of encouragement in the entire community to be involved in all the school activities and programs. Thus, there is a need for an intensive study and review on the strategies of the school in community involvement.

Apparently, this study will serve as a gateway to the raised concerns as it will determine the strategies of the school in community involvement particularly on the identified problems namely: a) parenting; b) communications; c) volunteering; d) learning at home; e) decision-making; and, f) collaborating with community. Moreover, it will consider the strategies that contribute to the success of the community involvement. The researcher is optimistic that this study will benefit the school in gaining valuable insights and skills in

designing and implementing strategies that will strengthen partnerships and involvement of the community. This may further help them impose due emphasis in the curriculum relevant activities and programs towards community involvement.

However, the school today strives in building a rapport with the community to come up with greater plans and programs. Further, these concerns are quite alarming as such requires effort to design strategies fitted not only with the concurring interests of the school but also the needs of the community. Through the involvement of teachers, parents and community, the School Based Management (SBM) can create more effective learning environment for learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the strategies of La Paz Elementary School to Enhance Community Involvement. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions

1. What is the extent of the strategies employed by the school to enhance community involvement as perceived by the teachers and parents along:
 - 1.1. parenting;
 - 1.2. communications;
 - 1.3. volunteering;
 - 1.4. learning at home;
 - 1.5. decision making; and
 - 1.6. collaborating with community?
2. What are the problems encountered by the school along the aforementioned dimensions and the degree of their severity as perceived by the teachers and parents?
3. Is there a significant difference between the strategies employed by the teachers and parents and the degree of severity of the problems encountered by the school as perceived by the teachers and parents?
4. What activities could be crafted to enhance the strategies being employed by La Paz Elementary School in community involvement?

Literature Review

Parents and community members are the key stakeholders in the School-Based Management (SBM) programs and decentralization measures in education. It is strongly argued that parental and community involvement is the key to ensure access and quality education provision. However, formal opportunities for parental involvement and community participation are neither always implemented nor necessarily translated into influence (Afridi, 2014).

Learners, schools, and families benefit if parents were supported in establishing home environments that foster children's growth and learning. Families whose basic needs of food, clothing or shelter are not being met have a more difficult time helping their children to do well in school. Schools and community agencies can work together to provide support so that parents can focus on their children's needs (Davis, 2010). His study is relevant to the present study because it involves different strategies that contributed to the increased community involvement of parents especially in supporting the needs of their children inside the school. Some of the strategies include designing effective forms of school-to-home and home-to-school communications about school programs and children's progress and providing information and ideas to families about how to help students at home with homework and other curriculum-related activities, decisions, and planning. Some of the results include smart communicating with parents and community members, encouraging positive parenting skills, increasing community awareness of the school, enhancing learning at home, including parents in decision – making and increasing community collaboration.

According to Gruber (2017), the more that parents and teachers share information with each other about students, the better equipped they will be to help those students become successful. Parents and teachers' consultation and collaboration create the climate for maximum realization of a student's potential. Effective communication with families means that the school welcomes and consistently supports families to support their children. Two-way communication about school programs and children's progress resulted in better outcomes of the students.

In the study of Ahmed (2010), it was found out that the best strategies to involve the community in school undertakings are the following: (1) encouraging positive parenting skills, (2) enhancing communication with families, (3) increasing volunteerism and attendance in school events, (4) enhancing learning at home, (5) increasing the number of parents in leadership and (6) decision making roles, and improving community collaborations. It was also emphasized that community involvement increases values and strategies in conducting research.

Likewise, according to the study of Cabardo (2016), the Levels of Participation of the School Stakeholders to the Different School-Initiated Activities and the Implementation of School-Based Management, he found out that the increased level of participation of the said stakeholders significantly affect the school manager to revisit strategies in conducting school activities at par and take necessary adjustments to such to further achieve the optimum level.

Meanwhile, in a study of European educators in European schools with parents' involvement in school governance, it was found out that enhancing family-school partnerships and increasing parent participation in educational decision-making can be highly effective for combatting early school leaving. Wide parental participation in decisions related to learning, as well as to the organization of the school and its activities, promotes transparency and better adjustment to actual family needs of and creates a greater sense of shared responsibility around education.

In support, Muthoni (2015) via the study of Fullon and Watson (2013), noted that in order to understand the school-community relationship one needs to; address the nature of the relationship that exists, how parents and teachers can work together for school improvement and how teachers can be integrated into the community.

Lastly, Crondahl and Karlsson (2015) found in their study that there are concurring factors that will aid community involvement and engagement. These are the trust and support which will be gained by school through involving parents in the planning and decision-making. If these two are practiced by school administrators towards the community, then success in their institution's goals will be achieved.

Generally, as it can be gleaned on the related literature and studies of the manuscript, it can be said with confidence that the more the parents and teachers are involved with each other about students and school progress, the better equipped they will be in helping those students and school become successful. Parents and teachers' consultation and collaboration create the climate for maximum realization of a student's potential. Henceforth, effective communication of school with families mean that the school welcomes and consistently supports families to reach out their children. Two-way communication about school programs and children's progress resulted in better outcomes of the students. As a result, the findings of this proposed study shall be very beneficial in enhancing the strategies the institution has to build for a better change.

Methodology

Respondents

In the implementation of the survey questionnaire on the strategies of La Paz Elementary School in Community Involvement, the researcher utilized fifteen (15) teachers and two hundred (200) parents and or guardians of La Paz Elementary School, a total of two hundred (215) respondents who attended and participated willingly in the administration of the questionnaire.

Procedure

The data gathering instrument used is a questionnaire adapted from the study of Davis (2010), Supporting Parent, Family, and Community Involvement in Your School. However, it was modified by the researcher in the context of the Educational system of the Philippines to localize according to the processes of school activities, programs, and projects. The constructed instrument is generalized that both parties - the teachers and the parents - as members of the community will answer the questions.

The instrument is a four-point likert-type scale questionnaire about the different strategies of schools in community involvement along categories namely: parenting, communications, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and collaborating with community.

Upon approval of by the members of the SDRC Team, the researcher prepared a letter addressed to the respondents, requesting their time and cooperation to attend a special meeting for the administration of the questionnaire. The researcher conducted a short orientation on the implementation of the research proposal and personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents. In so doing, she got some insights from the parents that are related to the study. The researcher ensured observation of the ethical standards in research and observed professionalism in the conduct of the research.

The researcher organized, classified and tallied the responses gathered according to group and according to the specific problems of the study.

Results and Discussion

Table 1.1 presents the strategies employed by the school in terms of parenting as perceived by teachers and parents. It can be gleaned from the table that the level of community involvement strategies employed by the school as perceived by the teachers and parents is extensive particularly in sponsoring home visiting programs or neighborhood meetings to help families understand schools and to help schools to understand families. This means that the activity is done every time because it is the most feasible way to communicate with parents and community people. This is parallel to the study of Graff (2017) who stated that home visits and meetings demonstrate teachers' support for learners' families and establish positive contact and communication among families towards parenting.

Meanwhile, the school lacks providing information, training, and assistance to all families who want it or who need it, not just to the few who can attend workshops or meetings at the school. This is supported in the study of (Barrera – Osorio, 2021) that parental involvement programs aim to strengthen home-school relations with the objective of improving educational outcomes. Schools should focus on conducting programs, trainings, providing information and assistance on marginalized or disadvantaged parents because such will contribute to higher school participation and improved communication between parents and schools. Parents are more likely to advocate for school support when they are familiar with how the school operates and understand the needs of the school and its

offerings.

Table 1.1. *Strategies Employed by the School in Terms of Parenting as Perceived by Teachers and Parents*

<i>The school...</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Parents</i>	
		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	Conducts workshops or provides information for parents on learner development.	3.40	Extensively	3.34	Extensively
2.	Provides information, training, and assistance to all families who want it or who need it, not just to the few who can attend workshops or meetings at the school.	2.92	Frequently	2.86	Frequently
3.	Produces information for families that is clear, usable, and linked to learner's success in school.	3.38	Extensively	3.35	Extensively
4.	Asks families for information about learner's goals, strengths and talents.	3.22	Frequently	3.21	Frequently
5.	Sponsors home visiting programs or neighborhood meetings to help families understand schools and to help schools to understand families.	3.54	Extensively	3.52	Extensively
6.	Provides families with information/ training on developing home conditions or environments that support learning.	3.32	Extensively	3.28	Extensively
7.	Respects the different cultures manifested by learner population.	3.42	Extensively	3.39	Extensively
<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>		3.31	Extensively	3.28	Extensively

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Never, 1.75-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.24 Frequently, 3.25-4.00 Extensively

In general, the extent of community involvement strategies in terms of parenting is extensively employed by the school as perceived by the teachers and parents which obtained the average weighted means of 3.31 and 3.28, respectively. This denotes that respondents value the roles of parents in the school as strong partners for the development of the school learners. Such claim is supported by Tekin (2011) in his study on parents' involvement in young children's education, it was noted that parents are considered to be the most important primary role models in their young children's immediate surroundings. Indeed, responsible parenting helps to ensure that a child develops the necessary skills and has the resources to succeed in and out of school.

Table 1.2. *Strategies Employed by the School in Terms of Communication as Perceived by Teachers and Parents*

<i>The school...</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Parents</i>	
		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	Review the readability, clarity, form, and frequency of all memo, notices, and other print and non-print communications.	2.56	Frequently	2.51	Frequently
2.	Develop communication for parents, who do not speak English well, do not read well, or need large type.	2.89	Frequently	2.75	Frequently
3.	Establish clear two-way channels for communications from home to school and from school to home.	2.48	Rarely	2.44	Rarely
4.	Conduct a formal conference with every parent at least once a year.	2.46	Rarely	2.45	Rarely
5.	Conduct an annual survey for families to share information and concerns about learner needs and reactions to school programs, and their satisfaction with their involvement in school.	3.42	Extensively	3.32	Extensively
6.	Conduct orientation for new parents.	3.46	Extensively	3.43	Extensively
7.	Send home folders of learner' work weekly or monthly for parent review and comment.	3.12	Frequently	3.10	Frequently
8.	Provide clear information about the curriculum, assessments, and achievement levels and report cards.	3.02	Frequently	2.98	Frequently
9.	Contact families of learners having academic or behavior problems.	3.58	Extensively	3.55	Extensively
10.	Develop school's plan and program of family and community involvement with input from educators, parents, and others.	3.12	Frequently	3.09	Frequently
11.	Assist teachers on the value and utility of contributions of parents and ways to build ties between school and home.	3.09	Frequently	3.08	Frequently
12.	Produce a regular school newsletter with up-to-date information about the school, special events, organizations, meetings, and parenting tips.	2.87	Frequently	2.85	Frequently
13.	Provide written communication in the language of the parents.	3.42	Extensively	3.36	Extensively
<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>		3.03	Frequently	2.99	Frequently

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Never, 1.75-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.24 Frequently, 3.25-4.00 Extensively

Table 1.2 shows the strategies employed by the school in terms of communication as perceived by the teachers and parents. The level of community involvement strategies of the school as perceived by the teachers and parents on contacting families of learners having academic or behavior problems is extensive as indicated by the weighted means of 3.58 and 3.55, respectively. This means that this activity is executed every time by the respondents. Such is important as to building a rapport with the parents which is consensus to Communication Theory of S. F. Scudder (2015) which states that all living beings existing on the planet communicate although the way of communication is different. One of the communication models is the Barnlund's Transactional Model which is a multi-layered

feedback system. This is a continuous process where sender and receiver interchange their places and both are equally important. The message passing takes place with a constant feedback being provided from both parties. A feedback for one is the message for the other. (Scott, n.d.)

Indeed, communications theory is vital for partnership and successful community involvement. If a teacher relays to a parent everything that has happened to a child, immediate intervention and upgrading of action may be given.

It could also be noted in the table that the level of community involvement strategies of the school as perceived by the teachers and parents on conducting a formal conference with every parent at least once a year is rare. This means that such relevant strategy is executed occasionally. Indeed, the respondents' formal conferences are typically done every time to contain their children's development needs an updates.

Hence, the level of community involvement strategies of the school in terms of communications as reflected in the table is frequently done based on the computed average weighted means of 3.03 and 2.99. This signifies that relevant strategies were often executed. Thus, the respondents pose good rapport with the community people which results to success among school children. This is supported by the statement of American Federation of Teachers (2019) that good two-way communication between families and schools is necessary for students' success. Related researches show also that the more parents and teachers share relevant information with each other about a student, the better equipped both will be to help that student achieve academically.

Table 1.3. *Strategies Employed by the School in terms of Volunteering as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents*

<i>Indicators</i> <i>The school...</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Parents</i>		
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	
1. Conducts an annual survey to identify interests, talents, and availability of parent volunteers, in order to match their skills/talents with school and classroom needs.	3.23	Frequently	3.21	Frequently	
2. Provides a parent/family room for volunteers and family members to work, meet, and access resources about parenting, childcare, tutoring, and other things that affect their children.	2.50	Frequently	2.52	Frequently	
3. Creates flexible volunteering and school events schedules, enabling parents who work to participate.	3.14	Frequently	3.11	Frequently	
4. Trains volunteers so they use their time productively.	2.50	Frequently	2.51	Frequently	
5. Recognizes volunteers for their time and efforts.	3.53	Extensively	3.50	Extensively	
6. Schedules school events at different times during the day and evening so that all families can attend some throughout the year.	3.23	Frequently	3.28	Extensively	
7. Reduces barriers to parent participation by providing transportation, childcare, flexible schedules, and addresses the needs of English-language learners.	2.52	Frequently	2.50	Frequently	
8. Encourages families and the community to be involved with the school in a variety of ways (assisting in classrooms, giving talks, monitoring halls, leading activities, etc.)	3.42	Extensively	3.38	Extensively	
	Average Weighted Mean	3.01	Frequently	3.00	Frequently

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Never, 1.75-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.24 Frequently, 3.25-4.00 Extensively

Table 1.3 shows that the level of community involvement strategies of the school as perceived by both the teachers and parents in recognizing volunteers for their time and efforts is extensive. This expresses that this strategy is executed every time since there are conduct of school recognitions monthly, quarterly and during commencement exercises; and that it can promote an empowered volunteering from the community (Florida Department of Education, 2019).

Consequently, Table 1.3 shows that the level of community involvement strategies of the school as perceived by the teachers and parents in terms of volunteering is found frequent as obtained by the average weighted means of 3.01 and 3.00, respectively. This means that relevant strategies in volunteering are often executed which implies that the school is persevering in encouraging parents and the community people in partaking their support to the school as it tightens partnership and involvement towards attaining a more conducive teaching-learning environment.

This is connected with Pelayo (2018) article entitled Stakeholders' Role in School-based Management. He reiterated that the stakeholders play an important role in managing schools. They are the partners of the schools and the leaders themselves in making the schools conducive to teaching and learning.

Table 1.4 shows that the level of community involvement strategies of the school in terms of learning at home is frequent as seen on the computed weighted means of 3.13 and 3.04, respectively. This suggests that relevant strategies were often executed which denotes that the respondents have a high regard of school-home learning and parental follow-ups or home-based guidance which make the school children learn more. This strengthened the theory of Jerome Bruner on scaffolding is a process through which an individual/learner moves from the supported to the independent level of learning. In this process there is an expert (either parents or teachers) source that provides help/support to the learner, while engaging in the process of completing an activity.

Table 1.4. *Strategies Employed by the School in Terms of Learning at Home as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents*

<i>Indicators The school...</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Parents</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Provides information to families on how to monitor and discuss schoolwork at home.	2.99	Frequently	2.90	Frequently
2. Provides ongoing and specific information to parents on how to assist students with skills that they need to improve.	3.02	Frequently	2.88	Frequently
3. Makes parents aware of the importance of reading at home, and asks parents to listen to their child read or read aloud with their child.	3.49	Extensively	3.37	Extensively
4. Assists families in helping students set academic goals, select courses, and programs.	3.12	Frequently	3.10	Frequently
5. Schedules regular interactive homework that requires students to demonstrate and discuss what they are learning with a family member.	3.02	Frequently	2.96	Frequently
Average Weighted Mean	3.13	Frequently	3.04	Frequently

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Never, 1.75-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.24 Frequently, 3.25-4.00 Extensively

Also, the aforementioned declaration is anchored to the DepEd New Hampshire (2012) which states that schools, parents, and the community should work together to promote the health, well-being, and learning of all students. When schools actively involve parents and engage community resources they are able to respond more effectively to the health-related needs of students. Family and community involvements foster partnerships among schools, family and community groups, and individuals. These partnerships result in sharing and maximizing resources. And they help children and youth develop healthy behaviors and promote healthy families.

Besides, according to Tyler, J. H. (2013) students, schools, and families benefited if parents were supported in establishing home environments that foster children’s growth and learning. Families whose basic needs of food, clothing or shelter are not being met have a more difficult time helping their children to do well in school. Schools and community agencies can work together to provide support so that parents can focus on their children’s needs.

Also, Alber (2014) explains the importance of the interactive, instructional relationship that tutors/teachers have in a learner's development, supporting that the attendance of others is significant for scaffolding skills acquisition and problem solving. They also emphasized on the importance for realizing the value of a solution to generate the sequence of steps that will lead to the solution of the problem, without scaffolding by an adult.

In connection of the theory in this study, the roles of parents in conducting follow-ups towards the progress of the child are essential in his development. Thus, teachers must establish a keen relationship with the parents of the learners so they may be guided at home.

Table 1.5. *Strategies Employed by the School in terms of Decision-Making as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents*

<i>Indicators The school...</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Parents</i>	
	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Has active PTA or other parent organizations.	3.52	Extensively	3.50	Extensively
2. Includes parent representatives on the school’s advisory council, improvement team, or other committees.	3.65	Extensively	3.55	Extensively
3. Has parents represented on district level advisory council and committees.	2.87	Frequently	2.82	Frequently
4. Involves parents in an organized, ongoing, and timely way in the planning, review, and improvement of programs.	2.80	Frequently	2.76	Frequently
5. Involves parents in revising the school/district curricula.	2.50	Frequently	2.50	Frequently
6. Includes parent leaders from all racial, ethnic, socioeconomic and other groups in the school.	2.54	Frequently	2.51	Frequently
7. Develops formal networks to link all families with their parent representatives.	3.12	Frequently	3.04	Frequently
8. Includes students (along with parents) in decision-making groups.	2.63	Frequently	2.55	Frequently
9. Deals with conflict openly and respectfully.	3.45	Extensively	3.44	Extensively
10. Asks involved parents to make contact with parents who are less involved to solicit their ideas, and report back to them.	2.58	Frequently	2.56	Frequently
Average Weighted Mean	2.95	Frequently	2.92	Frequently

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Never, 1.75-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.24 Frequently, 3.25-4.00 Extensively

Table 1.5 shows that the level of community involvement strategy of the school as perceived by the teachers and parents on including parent representatives on the school’s advisory council, improvement team, or other committees is extensive. This signifies that the strategy is executed every time. Indeed, the respondents have high esteem on the roles of the community that is viewed as strengthening community involvement.

Such is anchored to the statement of Afridi (2014) that parents and community members are the key stakeholders in the School-Based Management (SBM) programs and decentralization measures in education.

Likewise, according to Cabardo (2016) in his study on the Levels of Participation of the School Stakeholders to the Different School-Initiated Activities and the Implementation of School-Based Management, he found out that the increased level of participation of the said stakeholders significantly affect the school manager to revisit strategies in conducting school activities at par and take necessary adjustments to such to further achieve the optimum level.

Hence, Table 1.5 bespeaks that the level of community involvement strategies of the school in terms of decision making is frequent as indicated by the weighted means of 2.95 and 2.92, respectively. This implies that relevant strategies were often executed. Indeed, the respondents consider open-mindedness to decisions of the community people who directly connected with the school to boost their involvement to the institution. According to Qualifax (2019), parents earnestly involve themselves in school particularly in decision-making because they enormously willing and eager to take part in the welfare of their children.

Also, it strengthens the theory of Baraldi (2017) on social systems which is based on the distinction between system and environment. Baraldi (2017) further discussed that Luhmann’s theory of society combines the analysis of communication media, in particular, symbolically generalized media that make successful communication probable and internal differentiation of society. This analysis leads to understanding education as a subsystem of modern, functionally differentiated society.

In this study, social systems theory makes up the relevance of society in making policies in schools and that it makes up the whole system respond well to existing needs of the learners. With this theory, the school also is open to facilitating subsystems of either the organization or the society itself.

Table 1.6. *Strategies Employed by the School in Terms of Collaborating with the Community as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents*

<i>The school...</i>	<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Parents</i>	
		<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1.	Provides a community resource directory for parents and students with information on community services, programs, and agencies.	2.87	Frequently	2.83	Frequently
2.	Involves families in locating and utilizing community resources.	2.56	Frequently	2.55	Frequently
3.	Works with local businesses, industries, and community organizations on programs to enhance student skills and learning.	2.38	Rarely	2.30	Rarely
4.	Provides “one-stop” shopping for family services through partnership of school, counseling, health, recreation, job training, and other agencies.	2.02	Rarely	2.00	Rarely
5.	Opens its building for use by the community after school hours.	2.47	Rarely	2.43	Rarely
6.	Offers after-school programs for students with support from community businesses, agencies, and volunteers.	2.43	Rarely	2.37	Rarely
7.	Solves vague problems of responsibilities, funds, staff, and locations for collaborative activities to occur.	2.53	Frequently	2.57	Frequently
8.	Utilizes community resources, such as businesses, libraries, parks, and museums to enhance the learning environment.	2.67	Frequently	2.62	Frequently
Average Weighted Mean		2.49	Rarely	2.46	Rarely

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Never, 1.75-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.24 Frequently, 3.25-4.00 Extensively

Table 1.6 shows that the level of community involvement strategies of the school to provide “one-stop” shopping for family services through partnership of school, counseling, health, recreation, job training, and other agencies is rare. This signifies that such is executed occasionally which implies that the respondents are coordinated with the community.

Besides, based on the table, the level of community involvement strategies of the school as perceived by the teachers and parents in terms of collaborating with community is rare as obtained by the average weighted means of 2.49 and 2.46, respectively, which signifies that relevant strategies were executed occasionally. Thus, the respondents are keen in community errands.

Armstrong (2015) emphasized that schools that collaborate with the community promote partnerships that will increase parental involvement.

Table 1.7. *Summary Table of the Strategies Employed by the School as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Teachers</i>		<i>Parents</i>	
	<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>	<i>Average Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
Parenting	3.31	Extensively	3.28	Extensively
Communicating	3.03	Frequently	2.99	Frequently
Volunteering	3.01	Frequently	3.00	Frequently
Learning at Home	3.13	Frequently	3.04	Frequently
Decision-Making	2.95	Frequently	2.92	Frequently
Collaborating with the Community	2.49	Rarely	2.46	Rarely
Overall Weighted Mean	2.99	Frequently	2.95	Frequently

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Never, 1.75-2.49 Rarely, 2.50-3.24 Frequently, 3.25-4.00 Extensively

Table 1.7 shows the Summary Table of the Strategies Employed by the School as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents. Herewith, it can be gleaned on the table that the strategies employed by the school are frequently exercised as indicated by the overall weighted means of 2.99 (teachers) and 2.95 (parents). Among the indicators parenting obtained the highest weighted means of 3.31 (teachers) and 3.28 (parents) with descriptive equivalent of “Extensively”. In this result, it can be said that parenting has a great contribution in the community involvement since the parents are the most prevalent individuals in the activities and programs done inside and outside the school. Meanwhile the lowest weighted means were obtained by collaborating with the community strategies with average weighted means of 2.49 (teachers) and 2.46 (parents) with descriptive equivalent of “Rarely”.

Table 2.1. Problems Encountered by the School in terms of Parenting as Perceived by the Teachers and the Parents

Indicators	Teachers		Parents	
	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Bullying	1.48	Not Serious	1.46	Not Serious
Parents are having hard times on getting along with teachers which caused that they stay away from the school.	2.40	Moderately Serious	2.42	Moderately Serious
Problems at home- your parents' relationship, sibling issues, housing problem or simply feeling unsupported and labeled as trouble-maker.	1.52	Not Serious	1.55	Not Serious
Lack of financial support to go along with the demand of needs in the school.	2.04	Moderately Serious	2.06	Moderately Serious
Unsettled issues that gap the relationship of learners to teacher to parent.	1.45	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.78	Moderately Serious	1.79	Moderately Serious

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Not Serious, 1.75-2.49 Moderately Serious, 2.50-3.24 Serious, 3.25-4.00 Very Serious

Table 2.1 shows the problems encountered by the school in terms of parenting is moderately serious as indicated by an overall weighted mean of 1.78. This implies that some actions should be taken to address some issues and concerns in terms of parenting.

According to Sanders (2015), some ways to address parents' concerns is to engage them in school activities. He added that schools often don't engage parents because they don't think they can. Teachers perceive that families don't want to be involved when, in fact, families don't know how to be involved.

It can also be noted in Table 2.1 that among the indicators, parents having hard times on getting along with teachers which caused them to stay away from the school got the highest weighted means of 2.40 and 2.42. In the study of Muthoni (2015), parents have hard times to get along with teachers because of three main reasons: 1) they are shy with the poor performance of their children, 2) they are not aware if they have imparted good values to their children as manifested in their children's behaviour, and 3) some teachers are not easy to get along with / some teachers are not approachable.

Table 2.2. Problems Encountered by the School in terms of Communications as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents

Indicators	Teachers		Parents	
	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Poor letter and memorandum circulation for proper dissemination of meetings or symposiums.	2.07	Moderately Serious	2.05	Moderately Serious
The school provides unclear and understated letters caused to misunderstand its message.	1.56	Moderately Serious	1.55	Moderately Serious
The school does not recognize the voice of the community that sounds bossy at times.	1.45	Not Serious	1.43	Not Serious
There are no meetings and personal communications that happen in the school.	1.12	Not Serious	1.13	Not Serious
The school rarely conducts meetings.	1.24	Not Serious	1.23	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.49	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Not Serious, 1.75-2.49 Moderately Serious, 2.50-3.24 Serious, 3.25-4.00 Very Serious

Table 2.2 shows that as an overall assessment, the problems encountered by the teachers and parents in terms of communication are not serious as manifested by an overall weighted means of 1.49 and 1.48, respectively. This means that they regularly conduct meetings, there is personal communications that happen in school and they recognize the voice of the community.

On the contrary, looking at the indicators, two of them are described as moderately serious: poor letter and memorandum circulation for proper dissemination of meetings or symposiums and the school provides unclear and understated letters caused to misunderstand its message.

The result is parallel to the study of Ahmed (2010) that the leading problem encountered by the schools in terms of communication is poor and understated letters disseminated to parents. He noted that some parents were unable to attend school meetings and conferences because they don't clearly understand the content of the letters sent to them. He recommended that letters intended for parents should

be written in a language in which they could understand easily because some of the parents are not good or fluent in English.

Table 2.3. Problems Encountered by the School in terms of Volunteering as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents

Indicators	Parents		Teachers	
	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Most parents prioritize their work rather than to attend in school programs and activities (e.g. Brigada Eskwela, Clean-up Drive etc.)	3.04	Serious	3.05	Serious
There is lack of communication between the school and the community.	2.46	Moderately Serious	2.47	Moderately Serious
The school does not recognize the efforts and contribution of the community.	1.00	Not Serious	1.03	Not Serious
There are unsettled financial issues from the school linkages or alumni.	1.42	Not Serious	1.43	Not Serious
The school has lack of child support which caused relationship gap between the school and the community.	1.33	Not Serious	1.35	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.85	Moderately Serious	1.87	Moderately Serious

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Not Serious, 1.75-2.49 Moderately Serious, 2.50-3.24 Serious, 3.25-4.00 Very Serious

Further, Table 2.3 shows that generally, the problems encountered by the school in terms of volunteering is moderately serious as indicated by an average weighted means of 1.85 and 1.87. This implies that actions should be taken to address the problems encountered by the school in terms of recruiting and reorganizing parent support/ volunteering.

Among the indicators, the most serious problem encountered by the school in terms of volunteering is that most parents prioritize their work rather than to attend in school programs and activities such as Brigada Eskwela, Clean-up Drive, and etc.

The result of this study is in consonance with the study of Armstrong (2015) which revealed that majority of parents in primary schools are not attending school activities. He pointed out that the main reason why parents are unable to attend school activities is that they prioritize their sources of living. Secondly, some parents should stay at home to take care of their younger children.

Table 2.4. Problems Encountered by the School in Terms of Learning at Home as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents

Indicators	Teachers		Parents	
	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Most parents do not give follow-up instruction when child is at home.	2.12	Moderately Serious	2.13	Moderately Serious
Most parents do not have time with their children because they are focused in providing their financial needs.	3.52	Very Serious	3.55	Very Serious
The children do not have enough learning materials at home to use for studying.	2.45	Moderately Serious	2.47	Moderately Serious
There is lack of parents' appreciation and support in their child schooling. Simply no motivation at all for the pupils to study.	3.58	Very Serious	3.55	Very Serious
Poverty	2.36	Moderately Serious	2.39	Moderately Serious
Average Weighted Mean	2.81	Serious	2.82	Serious

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Not Serious, 1.75-2.49 Moderately Serious, 2.50-3.24 Serious, 3.25-4.00 Very Serious

Table 2.4 shows that generally, the problems encountered by the teachers and parents in terms of learning at home are serious as indicated by an average weighted means of 2.81 and 2.82, respectively. This implies that extensive solutions should be implemented to address the problems encountered by the school in terms of learning at home.

Two of the indicators were described as very serious problems: there is lack of parents' appreciation and support in their child schooling which leads unmotivated students to study and most parents do not have time with their children because they are focused in providing their financial needs.

This is parallel to the study of Baraldi (2017) which revealed that the leading problems encountered by teachers with regards to parental involvement are unsupportive parents and parents who lack time with their children to discuss school matters. His study emphasized that parental involvement not only enhances academic performance, but it also has a positive influence on student attitude and behavior. A parent's interest and encouragement in a child's education can affect the child's attitude toward school, classroom conduct, self-esteem, absenteeism, and motivation.

Table 2.5 presents the problems encountered by the teachers and parents in terms of decision-making was described as not serious as indicated by an overall weighted means of 1.43 and 1.45, respectively. As reflected in the table, it implies that the school recognizes the suggestions of barangay officials during meetings. It also implies that they consider inputs from their stakeholders.

Table 2.5. *Problems Encountered by the School in Terms of Decision-Making as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents*

Indicators	Teachers		Parents	
	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
There are lack of resources like time, staff, equipment and linkages.	1.34	Not Serious	1.35	Not Serious
Lack of adequate support either from the school to the community and vice versa.	1.22	Not Serious	1.27	Not Serious
The school suffers from dilemma if there are too many options in resolving problem or creating a new project.	1.32	Not Serious	1.37	Not Serious
The school does not recognize the suggestions of Barangay Officials during meetings.	1.00	Not Serious	1.05	Not Serious
Lack of effective strategies, plans, and poor dissemination of messages (letters, memos, etc.)	2.24	Moderately Serious	2.21	Moderately Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.43	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Not Serious, 1.75-2.49 Moderately Serious, 2.50-3.24 Serious, 3.25-4.00 Very Serious

From the indicators listed above, lack of effective strategies, plans, and poor dissemination of messages like letters and memorandums was considered as moderately serious. This is related to the result in Table 2.e about the problems encountered by the school in terms of communication which revealed that poor letter and memorandum circulation for proper dissemination of meetings or symposium was also moderately serious problem by the school.

The result is also parallel to the study of Ahmed (2010) which revealed that ineffective strategies, plan, and poor dissemination of messages like letters and memorandums can make parents unable to attend school meetings and conferences. His study also recommended that letters intended for parents should be written in a language in which they could understand easily because some of the parents are not good or fluent in English.

Table 2.6. *Problems Encountered by the School in Terms of Collaborating with the Community as Perceived by the Teachers and Parents*

Indicators	Teachers		Parents	
	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Parent involvement in school activities and program.	2.32	Moderately Serious	2.37	Moderately Serious
The school does not provide families with information on community activities.	1.42	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious
There are no organized after-school activities with support from community businesses, linkages and volunteers.	1.32	Not Serious	1.34	Not Serious
The school does not work with faith-based or any community programs to enhance pupil skills.	1.23	Not Serious	1.25	Not Serious
The school involves the community only when they are needed.	1.15	Not Serious	1.17	Not Serious
Average Weighted Mean	1.49	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious

Legend: 1.00-1.74 Not Serious, 1.75-2.49 Moderately Serious, 2.50-3.24 Serious, 3.25-4.00 Very Serious

Table 2.6 shows that as an overall assessment, the problems encountered by the teachers and parents in terms of collaborating with community was not serious as indicated by an overall weighted means of 1.49 and 1.52, respectively. This means that the school identify and integrate resources and services from the community to strengthen school programs, family practices, and student learning and development.

Among the indicators, parent involvement in school activities and program was considered as moderately serious problem by the teachers and parents. This was supported by the results that parents prioritize their work rather than attending school programs and activities. Since they prioritize their works, the parents were also unable to have time with their children and they lack support and appreciation to their children as also reflected in Table 2.c.

The study of Baraldi (2017), emphasized that parental involvement not only enhances academic performance, but it also has a positive influence on student attitude and behavior. A parent's interest and encouragement in a child's education can affect the child's attitude toward school, classroom conduct, self-esteem, absenteeism, and motivation.

Table 2.7 shows that the respondents obtained an overall weighted means of 1.81 and 1.82 denoting a descriptive equivalent of "Moderately Serious". Among the indicators, learning at home obtained the highest weighted means of 2.81 and 2.82 denoting a descriptive equivalent of "Serious" while decision-making obtained the lowest average weighted means of 1.43 and 1.45 denoting a descriptive equivalent of "Not Serious".

In this regard, learning from home is a very hard situation nowadays, it has been so serious to address because most parents and learners are still in the adoption of the new educational system.

Table 2.7. Summary Table Problems Encountered by the School as Perceived by the Teachers

Indicators	Average Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	Average Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Parenting	1.79	Moderately Serious	1.79	Moderately Serious
Communicating	1.49	Not Serious	1.48	Not Serious
Volunteering	1.85	Moderately Serious	1.87	Moderately Serious
Learning at Home	2.81	Serious	2.82	Serious
Decision-Making	1.43	Not Serious	1.45	Not Serious
Collaborating with the Community	1.49	Not Serious	1.52	Not Serious
Overall Weighted Mean	1.81	Moderately Serious	1.82	Moderately Serious

Table 3.1 presents that strategies employed by the school in community involvement have significant relationships with their problems encountered by teachers along those strategies. That is, strategies employed by the school in terms of parenting have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of parenting; strategies employed by the school in terms of volunteering have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of volunteering; strategies employed by the school in terms of communications have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of communications.

Table 3.1. Significant Relationship between the Strategies Employed by the School as Perceived by the Teachers and the Degree of Severity of the Problems Encountered by the School as Perceived by the Teachers

Variables	r-value	p-value	Interpretation	Decision	
Parenting	Parenting	.782	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Communications	-.122	.209	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Volunteering	.462	.178	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	.242	.176	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision Making	.234	.098	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Communications	Collaborating w/ Com	.418	.323	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Communications	.877	.003	Significant	Reject Ho
	Volunteering	-.298	.398	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	-.233	.329	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision Making	.209	.489	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Volunteering	Collaborating w/ Com	-.392	.323	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Volunteering	.709	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	.278	.462	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision Making	.390	.309	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Learning at Home	Collaborating w/ Com	.208	.275	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	.921	.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Decision Making	-.352	.527	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Decision-Making	Collaborating w/ Com	.234	.372	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision-Making	.881	.007	Significant	Reject Ho
Collaborating w/ Com	Collaborating w/ Com	.403	.508	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Collaborating w/ Com	Collaborating w/ Com	.709	.000	Significant	Reject Ho

Note: significant at 5% level alpha

Moreover, strategies employed by the school in terms of learning at home have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of learning at home; strategies employed by the school in terms of decision-making have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of decision-making; and strategies employed by the school in terms of collaborating with community have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of collaborating with community.

In this regard, the relationship between the strategies employed by the school as perceived by the teachers and the degree of severity of the problems encountered by the School as perceived by the teachers is not significant. As such, the hypothesis of the study is rejected. It is also extracted in this study that there are problems like, most parents prioritize their work rather than to attend in school programs and activities (e.g. Brigada Eskwela, Clean-up Drive etc.), most parents do not have time with their children because they are focused in providing their financial needs, there is lack of parents' appreciation and support in their child schooling. Simply no motivation at all for the pupils to study.

Thus, improving the strategies employed by the school can address the problems encountered by the teachers. Like, orienting parents on the importance of parental involvement in the education of their children and orienting parents on the importance of time management.

Table 3.2 shows that strategies employed by the school in community involvement have significant relationships with their problems encountered by parents along those strategies. That is, strategies employed by the school in terms of parenting have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of parenting; strategies employed by the school in terms of

volunteering have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of volunteering; strategies employed by the school in terms of communications have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of communications; strategies employed by the school in terms of learning at home have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of learning at home; strategies employed by the school in terms of decision-making have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of decision-making; and strategies employed by the school in terms of collaborating with community have significant relationship with the problems encountered by the school in terms of collaborating with community. Thus, improving the strategies employed by the school can address the problems encountered by the parents.

Table 3.2. *Significant Relationship Between the Strategies Employed by the School as Perceived by the Parents and the Degree of Severity of the Problems Encountered by the School as Perceived by the Parents*

Variables		r- value	p- value	Interpretation	Decision
Parenting	Parenting	0.765	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Communications	-0.139	0.188	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Volunteering	0.445	0.157	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	0.225	0.155	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision Making	0.217	0.077	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Communications	Collaborating w/ Com	0.401	0.302	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Communications	0.86	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Volunteering	-0.315	0.377	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	-0.25	0.308	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision Making	0.192	0.468	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Volunteering	Collaborating w/ Com	-0.409	0.302	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Volunteering	0.692	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	0.261	0.441	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision Making	0.373	0.288	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Learning at Home	Collaborating w/ Com	0.191	0.254	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Learning at Home	0.904	-0.021	Significant	Reject Ho
	Decision Making	-0.369	0.506	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Decision-Making	Collaborating w/ Com	0.217	0.351	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
	Decision-Making	0.864	-0.014	Significant	Reject Ho
	Collaborating w/ Com	0.386	0.487	Not Significant	Do Not Reject Ho
Collaborating w/ Com	Collaborating w/ Com	0.692	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho

Note: significant at 5% level alpha

Conclusions

One of the advocacies of this research is to use the best strategies that will increase the involvement of the community in school activities. Another is to encourage teachers and school heads to conduct their own research. The researcher will seek approval of the Schools Division Superintendent for the dissemination of the findings of the study. The results will be presented through the different seminars and Learning Action Cells (LAC) Sessions that will be conducted in the school, district or division. The findings of this study could be used by school leaders in formulating, implementing, and evaluating their practices or strategies in community involvement. It will help them formulate more definite plans of action to improve further leadership. The result will be communicated to the proper authorities.

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